

MONTE CARLO SIMULATION
AND PORTFOLIO
OPTIMISATION, A CASE STUDY

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Abstract

The Monte Carlo Simulation consists of simulating a stochastic model several times, to estimate the probability distribution of the stochastic model. It yields information such as volatility and average return, that can be used to forecast financial events' probabilities.

The Monte Carlo Simulation is extensively used in economics and finance, but few papers in the literature review access its effectivity properly. Moreover, most papers apply the method without considering proper economics and finance theories such as the Capital Asset Pricing Model and the Modern Portfolio Theory. Therefore, this paper accessed the literature related, and tried to fill its gaps.

Finally, a portfolio was build considering appropriated theories, and its allocation optimised by the Monte Carlo Simulation. The optimised portfolio's performance was compared to a random allocated portfolio. The optimised portfolio attended the theoretical demands established when the portfolio was built, while the random portfolio, even more profitable, performed the opposite of what was expected from the portfolio's characteristics.

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Introduction

The Monte Carlo simulation (MCS) is widely used in economics and finance. This work studied papers that applied the MCS in scenarios relevant to economics and finance as risk management, monetary policy, and portfolio optimisation. Gaps in the literature related were found, as the lack of theories when building models. Then, an empirical test was done addressing those gaps to test the model properly.

The MCS consists of simulating a stochastic model several times, to estimate the probability distribution of the stochastic model. The simulation yields information as standard deviation, mean and variance, to possibly forecast movements and assign probabilities to possible outcomes (Platon and Constantinescu, 2014).

The MCS literature has been used as a tool by the ECB in the calibration of policies, which aim to preserve the stability in a financial system that affects many economies in the EU. Showing the power and reliability of the method.

The review concludes that the literature related has problems of synergy when it comes to consider different theories and methods, as well as constantly failing to apply theory and empiricism together. Therefore, the capital asset pricing model (CAPM) and the modern portfolio theory (MPT) were analysed and used to build the module, helping to fill the literature's gaps. This subject was chosen, because the MCS is widely used, but poorly tested for economics and finance.

Finally, the forecasts produced by the MCS are usually not empirically evaluated. Therefore, a portfolio was built considering important economic theories, and tested in the real world, aiming to answer the essay question; Does the MCS work for a process such as assigning weights to optimise a portfolio?

Literature Review

ECB Literature

The European Central Bank (ECB) used the MCS in many studies. Lombardi and Sgherri (2007) applies a neo-Keynesian model to evaluate the US monetary policy and concludes that interest rates are being held too low. The MCS was used to perform predictive checks on the Federal Reserve's actions. Even though the in-sample fit of the model is quite accurate, having no major divergences between actual and predicted values, the model tends to underpredict the interest rate volatility, due to the assumption of a frictionless market.

The ECB also used the MCS to discover the origin of systemic risk, which is the probability of a substantial number of banks going to distress altogether (Montagna, Torri and Covi, 2020), that may cause banks' losses from the exposure to the real economy. The model is not just used to calculate the probability of systemic risk events, but bank default probability. After applying the stochastic model, the paper concludes that regulators pursuing the reduction of banks' default have little effect in reducing the probability of facing systemic risk. Thus, regulators need to decide if they want to avoid average default probability or fewer banks defaulting simultaneously.

Even though Lombardi and Sgherri (2007), and Montagna, Torri and Covi (2020) simulations brought enough information to help calibrating policies to be undertaken by the ECB, both cases fail to explain a gap in the related literature. If the methodology expects frictionless markets (Lombardi and Sgherri, 2007), how can it be used to predict banks defaulting (Montagna, Torri and Covi, 2020), if it causes and is caused by economic shocks or "frictions" in the market?

The ECB also used the methodology to evaluate the performance of popular Value at Risk (VaR) methodologies (Manganelli and Engle, 2001). VaR is the possible loss in a portfolio caused by unfavourable market movements. VaR aims to reduce the portfolio's risk to a number, associated to a certain probability.

Among the common methodologies used for VaR, the MCS showed that Conditional Autoregressive Value at Risk models produce the best estimates with heavy-tailed data-generating-processes. The study also presents a regression-based method, aiming to estimate the expected shortfall. The MCS indicated that the regression method tends to outperform the Extreme Value Theory approach at 1% and 5% confidence levels (Manganelli and Engle, 2001). However, to generate data the paper uses GARCH processes, diminishing the academic importance of the model (Brooks, 2019).

Portfolio Management

When applying the MCS in a portfolio, assumptions need to be made (Cong and Oosterlee, 2016). It makes the simulation mutable in different papers, almost every study will assume different premisses, that may clash with MPT assumptions. Moreover, both the MCS and the MPT make similar assumptions considered weak such as the debatable perfect market's assumption (Mangram E., 2013). A paper that does not address this weakness can end up facing the same criticism.

Two different portfolio optimisation approaches are tested in a case study conducted by Pedersen (2014), the Markowitz mean-variance and Kelly geometric-mean. The mean-variance optimised portfolios were found to not minimise risk, while Kelly portfolios were found to optimise against risk, but are usually built in few assets, hence sensitive to estimation errors.

The Kelly portfolio is built to maximise the logarithmic growth-rate, allowing a sequence of bets in the long-run to outperform the market on average. However, the Kelly betting only aims to maximise the logarithmic growth-rate, the asset limit is increased, where the worse performing assets (considering Kelly values) are removed from the portfolio. The case study started with a portfolio made of S&P500, McDonald's, US government bonds, Wal-Mart, and Coca-cola, and ended up having all assets removed from the portfolio, except Coca-Cola that maximised the Kelly value, table.1. It clashes with a MPT assumption of diversification to diminish unsystematic risk (Mangram E., 2013).

Weight Bounds	Portfolio Weights (Long Only)					Value Yield		Kelly	
	S&P 500	Coca-Cola	Wal-Mart	McDonald's	Gov. Bond	Mean	Stdev	Value	Pr*
[0, 0.1]	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.6	6.8%	0.2%	0.0658	0.0
[0, 0.2]	0.2	0.2	0.2	0.2	0.2	10.1%	0.3%	0.0962	0.0
[0, 0.3]	0.3	0.3	0.3	0.1	0.0	12.5%	0.4%	0.1178	1.0
[0, 0.4]	0.2	0.4	0.4	0.0	0.0	13.9%	0.5%	0.1300	1.0
[0, 0.5]	0.0	0.5	0.5	0.0	0.0	15.2%	0.6%	0.1415	1.0
[0, 0.6]	0.0	0.6	0.4	0.0	0.0	15.5%	0.7%	0.1441	1.0
[0, 0.7]	0.0	0.7	0.3	0.0	0.0	15.8%	0.8%	0.1467	1.0
[0, 0.8]	0.0	0.8	0.2	0.0	0.0	16.1%	1.0%	0.1493	1.0
[0, 0.9]	0.0	0.9	0.1	0.0	0.0	16.4%	1.1%	0.1519	1.0
[0, 1.0]	0.0	1.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	16.7%	1.2%	0.1545	1.0

Table 1: Kelly optimal portfolio weights, long-only. All assets except from Coca-Cola would be removed with time, to maximise the Kelly value. Holding period is eternity. (Pedersen, 2014, pg.94).

Alternatively, the mean-variance optimal portfolio seeks to have the maximum mean and minimum variance (Pedersen, 2014). For that reason, McDonalds is present in most of the portfolio's efficient frontier, table.2, even though it has a lower value yield than the other assets in the portfolio. It

happens because McDonalds has a low variance, hence optimising the mean-variance frontier. The author criticises the mean-variance method, because it would not be good measuring risk without considering neither the probability of loss, nor the probability of other assets having a higher return.

	Portfolio Weights (Long Only)				Value Yield	
	S&P 500	Coca-Cola	Wal-Mart	McDonald's	Mean	Stdev
Inefficient Frontier	0.000	0.000	0.000	1.000	0.079	0.004
	0.523	0.000	0.013	0.463	0.084	0.004
	0.475	0.000	0.100	0.425	0.089	0.003
	0.424	0.014	0.166	0.397	0.093	0.003
	0.371	0.030	0.229	0.370	0.098	0.003
	0.319	0.046	0.292	0.344	0.102	0.003
	0.266	0.062	0.354	0.318	0.107	0.003
Min-Variance	0.240	0.070	0.385	0.305	0.110	0.003
Efficient Frontier	0.214	0.078	0.417	0.291	0.112	0.003
	0.162	0.094	0.480	0.265	0.116	0.003
	0.109	0.109	0.543	0.238	0.121	0.003
	0.057	0.125	0.605	0.212	0.126	0.003
	0.005	0.141	0.668	0.186	0.130	0.003
	0.000	0.157	0.726	0.117	0.135	0.003
	0.000	0.172	0.783	0.045	0.139	0.004
	0.000	0.239	0.761	0.000	0.144	0.004
	0.000	0.391	0.609	0.000	0.149	0.005
	0.000	0.543	0.457	0.000	0.153	0.006
	0.000	0.696	0.304	0.000	0.158	0.008
	0.000	0.848	0.152	0.000	0.163	0.010
	0.000	1.000	0.000	0.000	0.167	0.012

Table 2: Mean-variance portfolio weights, long-only. McDonalds is in most of the efficient frontier, even giving lower returns, as it has lower variance. Holding period is eternity. (Pedersen, 2014, pg.89).

CAPM

Developed initially by Sharpe in 1964, the CAPM shows how the capital market establishes share prices (Pike et al., 2012). The CAPM helps to describe risk and separate market return against your return, aiming to beat the market. It is nowadays used in modern financial theories and will be considered in this study.

A portfolio is a set of weighted securities, where return is defined as:

$$r_p(t) = \sum_i^n w_i r_i(t) \quad (\text{Equation 1})$$

The returns (r) of our portfolio at a time (t) is equal to the sum from (i) to the (n) number of securities times its weights, multiplied by the returns on time “ t ”. In other words, it is the weight times a return for each specific stock, and then you sum all of them up for giving the return of your portfolio (Portilla, 2022).

When used with the MCS to build up a portfolio, the CAPM can be translated into the following equation:

$$r_i(t) = \beta_i r_m(t) + \alpha_i(t) \quad (\text{Equation 2})$$

The return of “ i ” of time “ t ” is equal to beta, multiplied by a return of “ m ” times “ t ” plus alpha at time “ t ”. Equation 2 describes the return of security “ i ” encompassed of two terms, the beta term that implies that the return of a security is equal to the return of the market times the beta factor, plus the residual alpha term.

This CAPM equation (2) means the return of a specific security “ i ” at time “ t ” is equal to a specific beta value for the security of “ i ” multiplied by the return of the entire market at time “ t ”. Therefore, if beta equal to 1, this security moves together with the market, if beta is 2 it moves twice as much as the market. However, as the stock “ i ” is unlikely to match exactly with the beta term, some alpha term is added. Nevertheless, the CAPM states that this alpha is expected to be zero (Portilla, 2022).

The MCS will be used in this paper to challenge this assumption that alpha cannot be predicted, at least at some extent, and thus profit from it.

Risk and Return

When explaining the risk and return associated to the CAPM, Pike et al. (2012) presented the idea of total shareholder return (TSR), where the dividend paid is considered. The TSR is neglected sometimes in the literature, and it is important as it affects risk and liquidity. If a share is not volatile, neither offering great losses nor gains, however pays consistent dividends, holding it diminishes risks and increases predictability.

Considering the MPT and the CAPM to build a modern portfolio, diversification needs to be considered. As the number of securities increases, the variability of the portfolio return, measured by the standard deviation, diminishes because the exposure to volatile securities can be overcome by adding lower risk securities to the portfolio, or even higher risk if the return is not correlated.

The CAPM states there are two risks that must be considered. Specific risk, the variability in return related on factors of an individual company. And systematic risk, the variability in return due to factors that influence the whole market, also called market risk. To reduce the specific risk, a portfolio should comprise at least between 25-30 securities (Pike et al., 2012), represented in figure.1.

Figure 1: Diminishing specific risk with diversification. Based on Pike, Neale and Linsley (2012, pg.209)

As specific risk can be diversified by building a portfolio, rational investors expect to be rewarded by bearing only systematic risk, that can be set as a line relating the expected return on the particular security, to the return expected on the market, represented by equation 2.

Getting back to the equation 2, we can focus on beta, that is the covariance of the return on security “j” with the return on the market, divided by the markets return:

$$Beta_j = \frac{COV_{jm}}{\sigma_m}$$

Beta measurement is done looking forward as people’s expectations are hard to record. If the past is accepted as a reliable indicator of the future, beta can indicate how the company “j” is influenced by variations in the market “m”. However, beta does not measure risk in absolute terms, it is a risk indicator that presents the return of a single asset’s relation to the overall market return, therefore it measures just relative risk. Risk in absolute terms is measured by analysis of variance, comprising both systematic risk and specific risk (Pike et al., 2012).

However, even the CAPM have weaknesses. First, it relies on a risk-free asset, which might not exist in the real world, as even countries can default, as Greece did. Second, the analysis that can be drawn using the CAPM relies on using a benchmark. But as no benchmark captures all stocks, the analysis can be distorted. Finally, the CAPM is restrictive as it does not include all forms of assets, just securities, leaving for example rare coins and real state out of the analysis. Thus, the CAPM only prices securities (Pike et al., 2012).

Expectations

In the literature reviewed, straight conclusions were derived by using the MCS. Especially in the ECB and portfolio management literatures.

This experiment's result is expected to be straightforward. However, differently from the literature related, many theories will be used, and ponderations might be needed in the conclusion. The MCS is expected to be relevant, this study aims to find at what extent it is relevant.

Methodology

This coursework aims to fill the gap in the literature related, also by presenting a consistent research philosophy, term that refers to a system of assumptions about the development of knowledge (Saunders et al., 2019).

With an epistemological approach, this study objectively seeks to discover the truth about a method, the MCS, through observable and measurable facts, where generalisations can be drawn. Even though many theories were used to build the model, this study draws conclusion through observation, and is therefore highly empirical. The theories serve as lenses to which the empirical case study will see the truth.

Moreover, a deductive approach will be applied, as this research started with theories such as the MPT, the MCS, and the CAPM, that were developed from reading the academic literature and after designed to evaluate the theory. Three characteristics of deductive approach were observed; the search for explaining causal relationships among concepts and variables; the operationalisation of concepts to enable facts to be measured quantitatively; and the ability to properly create generalisation, where the model can be replicated if needed, by any investor who holds an ISA account and a computer.

This study is therefore quantitative and deductive, as data is collected and analysed to test theory, using statistical and graphical techniques.

The purpose of this study is to establish causal relations between variables, hence an explanatory study. This paper aims not just to explain “how” or “if” the MCS works when assigning weights to build a portfolio, but also “to what extent”, containing also a strong evaluative purpose. The theoretical contribution this study aims to give is “how effective” the MCS is.

Finally, this is a case study that tries to capture a real-life context, structured with the intention to proceed in a linear way. Literature is reviewed first, the research question defined, project designed, data collected, analysed, reported, and interpreted (Saunders et al., 2019). This study brings realist philosophical assumptions.

Data

This paper used data provided through the Bloomberg Terminal (Bloomberg, 2022). This consists of the price movement since 19/02/2014 to 19/02/2019 of companies established in the UK, and its betas. The portfolio was formed according to the following CAPM and MPT guidelines:

The TSR approach is used, considering the price movement plus dividends reinvested in a period. It is more realistic than evaluating an asset just based on its price movement, and avoids overreliance in assets that are more volatile, making the whole portfolio more volatile. TSR is calculated as follows:

$$R_{jt} = \frac{D_{jt} + (P_{jt} - P_{jt-1})}{P_{jt-1}} \times 100 \quad (\text{Equation 3}) \quad (\text{Pike et al., 2012})$$

D_{jt} is the dividend per share paid by company j on period t , and P_{jt} is the company's j share price at the end of period t .

Between 25-30 securities is a suitable number to diversify a portfolio. It is, however, impractical both to investors and to this paper. Therefore, the ETF VUKE, that mimics the FTSE100 index was added to the portfolio. The FTSE100 is effective for this purpose (Pike et al., 2012) as it has 100 stocks and constitutes 81% of the whole UK's market capitalisation and sets our benchmark for the UK (Pike et al., 2012). The VUKE has $\beta=1.001$.

Gold was chosen due to its negative beta and its historical importance in portfolios. The ETC PHGP, that mimics gold prices, and is pound denominated, was added to balance the portfolio in case of downturns with $\beta=-0.043$.

Gilts were also added, as studies usually consider bonds when building portfolios (Pedersen, 2014). The ETF VGOV, that tracks the Bloomberg Sterling Gilt Float Adjusted Index, with a $\beta=0.049$ was added to the portfolio.

Shell was added as it is a well-established company in the UK and adds more expected returns (and risk) to the portfolio, $\beta=1.387$.

To follow the CAPM motto of "selling umbrellas and sun-cream at the same time", INRG, a clean energy ETF, was added to diversify against Shell. INRG also fills the requisite needed to follow CAPM and MPT guidelines, investing in international companies (Pike et al., 2012), as the ETF is formed by "green" companies worldwide, $\beta=1.024$.

The assets were put together in an array, and its normalised returns for the period are shown in figure.2. Observing the normalised returns, PHGP and SHEL (the ticker for Shell) are the most profitable, and volatile assets for the period. While VGOV and VUKE have a clear upward trend with a lower volatility. INRG is also volatile. The daily log return, figure.3, confirms the analysis, and shows that VGOV and PHGP have longer tails towards positive returns.

Figure 2: Portfolio's normalised returns 2014 to 2019.

Figure 3: Portfolio's log daily return 2014 to 2019.

Fig.4 shows the Kernel density estimation, estimating the distribution of the underlying assets' log return. VGOV and VUKE are expected to rely much more in the average than SHEL, PHGP, and INRG, the last two heavy tailed, but PHGP more towards exceptional gains.

Figure 4: Kernel Density Estimate 2014 to 2019.

Table.3 displays the portfolio's daily logarithmic returns mean, standard deviation, minimum and maximum return. PHGP presents high return and volatility, while SHEL and INRG the highest volatilities and losses. VGOV is again the most stable asset, with lower risks, lower volatility, but with a mean higher than PHGP and VUKE, meaning that the lower volatility in this case is bringing more consistent gains.

	count	mean	std	min	25%	50%	75%	max
VUKE	1288.0	0.000186	0.008164	-0.044329	-0.004105	0.000432	0.004366	0.043370
PHGP	1288.0	0.000186	0.009114	-0.033097	-0.004609	-0.000257	0.004894	0.121917
VGOV	1288.0	0.000188	0.004310	-0.013345	-0.002290	0.000208	0.002857	0.023380
SHEL	1288.0	0.000270	0.012962	-0.063886	-0.006387	0.000175	0.007070	0.054084
INRG	1288.0	0.000200	0.012226	-0.054934	-0.006196	0.000394	0.007368	0.054809

Table 3: Logarithmic returns transposition, 2014 to 2019.

The covariance and correlation, tables 3 and 4, show the theoretical considerations of the CAPM and the MPT in fact create a diversified portfolio.

	VUKE	PHGP	VGOV	SHEL	INRG
VUKE	0.016797	-0.002205	-0.001881	0.017533	0.015766
PHGP	-0.002205	0.020934	0.003828	0.001652	0.001487
VGOV	-0.001881	0.003828	0.004681	-0.002209	-0.001583
SHEL	0.017533	0.001652	-0.002209	0.042340	0.019020
INRG	0.015766	0.001487	-0.001583	0.019020	0.037668

Table 4: Covariance 2014 to 2019.

	VUKE	PHGP	VGOV	SHEL	INRG
VUKE	1.000000	-0.117583	-0.212156	0.657446	0.626767
PHGP	-0.117583	1.000000	0.386671	0.055490	0.052970
VGOV	-0.212156	0.386671	1.000000	-0.156910	-0.119228
SHEL	0.657446	0.055490	-0.156910	1.000000	0.476274
INRG	0.626767	0.052970	-0.119228	0.476274	1.000000

Table 5: Correlation 2014 to 2019.

Does the MCS really work for a process such as assigning weights to optimise a portfolio?

This study aims to assess the MCS for economics and finance purposes, such as optimise a portfolio. The portfolio's performance will be tested and compared to the same portfolio not optimised by the MCS.

Therefore, the portfolio was not built with the intention of beating the market or creating a profitable or perfect portfolio, the returns of the portfolio does not interest to this study's conclusion. But whether this return is higher, less volatile, or less risky when using the MCS. What interest is whether the MCS optimise this portfolio or not.

The portfolio's average beta of 0.664, considered risk averse, does not constitute an investor's characteristic and was randomly achieved when following theoretical demands.

The optimised portfolio is found by simulating 150,000 possible portfolio allocations, creating an array that can return the combination that brings the higher return with the lowest volatility, the best Sharpe ratio. This combination is plotted on figure.5, the red dot is the optimised portfolio among other possible allocations.

Figure 5: MCS efficient frontier plot, red dot is the optimised portfolio 2014 to 2019.

This portfolio is then tested against a random portfolio, which is not optimised.

To create the random portfolio, an average of five random allocations was taken plus the average of the 150,000 portfolio simulations. A simple average of the 150,000 random portfolios cannot be taken, as it returns [0.2, 0.2, 0.2, 0.2, 0.2], the average random allocations for five weights that sum up to one. Which ironically is just the average, but not a simple set of random numbers.

Findings

The data used to build the portfolios is 02/19/2014 to 02/19/2019. The empirical test ranges from 02/03/2019 to 02/03/2022.

Table.6 presents the random and table.7 the optimised portfolio. The random portfolio has a higher average daily return, Sharpe ratio, and volatility in relation to the optimised portfolio, and an average beta more than three times higher.

RANDOM Portfolio						
	VUKE	PHGP	VGOV	SHEL	INRG	Portfolio (Total)
weights	0.24	0.1998	0.1168	0.182	0.2614	1.000
daily ret	0.00003504	0.00009710	0.00000969	-0.00000109	0.00023343	0.00037418
daily std	0.00228912	0.00195924	0.00068643	0.00280535	0.00495641	0.012696546
					Sharpe ratio	0.029470645
Beta	0.24024	-0.0085914	-0.0057232	0.252434	0.2676736	0.746033

Table 6: Random portfolio results, 2019-2022.

OPTIMISED Portfolio						
	VUKE	PHGP	VGOV	SHEL	INRG	Portfolio (Total)
weights	0.158	0.0448	0.71	0.0666	0.0206	1.000
daily ret	0.0000231	0.0000218	0.0000589	-0.0000004	0.0000184	0.0001218
daily std	0.0015070	0.0004393	0.0041727	0.0010266	0.0003906	0.007536152
					Sharpe ratio	0.016157716
Beta	0.158158	-0.001926	-0.03479	0.0923742	0.0210944	0.2349102

Table 7: Optimised portfolio results, 2019-2022.

The optimised portfolio assigned 71% weight to VGOV, while PHGP had less than 5% weight. The random portfolio weighted almost 20% in gold, the asset with the best Sharpe ratio for the period, 2019-2022. This is the biggest difference in those two portfolios, and the reason the optimised portfolio ended up with a lower Sharpe ratio.

Normalised returns, figure.2, shows great shocks and volatility in the gold market, a downturn in 2015, and a steep increase in 2016 followed by a correction in 2017, ending the sample period (02-2019) below 2016 prices. All this volatile annualization was captured by the MCS, causing an output fewer than 5% to assign to the asset. Also, the sample period ended just before another event where gold outperformed the market, the Covid-19 crash in 2020, not being captured by the model. Shell has a similar movement for the sample period (2014-2019), ending it with impressive returns. But, due to volatility, the MCS algorithm assigned 6% to it, being essential to minimising risk and losses during the test period (2019-2022). For the same reason, INRG was assigned just 2% weight by the MCS.

In the optimised portfolio, VUKE and VGOV, were assigned the heavier weights, 15.8% and 71%, probably because both paid consistent dividends (monthly for VGOV) and had a clear upward trend. PHGP (gold), does not pay dividends, holding it was dangerous considering its volatility compared to

VUKE and VGOV. If the investor needed money in the middle of a downturn, they musted sell it in high losses without collecting dividends.

Figure.6, shows the assets daily return for 2019-2022. Comparing to 2014-2019, the tails of PHGP and SHEL are quite different. PHGP still heavy tailed towards gains, but with a more centred skewness, while SHEL has both tails longer, showing an increase in volatility. INRG is heavy tailed to the left, accumulating more days with consistent losses. Therefore, the MCS assigned most of the weights to assets with lower volatility and risk, losing sometimes big price movements as offered by PHGP, but also avoiding huge losses for the period as SHEL and INRG experienced.

Figure 6: Portfolio's empirical test logarithmic daily return 2019 to 2022.

Figure.7 shows the KDE for the test (2019-2022), where VGOV and VUKE are estimated, again, to be more reliable and predictable, and move around the mean. INRG and SHEL have a heavy tailed KDE, showing lower reliability and predictability on daily return (losses). Therefore, the three assets minimised by the MCS are those less reliable and less predictable in both the data sample, 2014-2019 and the test 2019-2022.

Figure 7: Empirical test's Kernel density estimate 2019 to 2022.

Table.8, shows the performance during the testing period, 2019-2022. PHGP performed almost six times more than VGOV in the average daily return. PHGP and INRG had the best average daily return, but SHEL the worst. SHEL and INRG achieved the highest daily losses and return, (min and max columns), but SHEL's average daily return is negative. VUKE also had relatively high daily losses and returns, while its average return is relatively low. VUKE performed well most of the period but suffered by shocks caused by Covid-19.

	count	mean	std	min	25%	50%	75%	max
VUKE	759.0	0.000146	0.009538	-0.081088	-0.003665	0.000511	0.004763	0.062951
PHGP	759.0	0.000486	0.009813	-0.049732	-0.004422	0.000539	0.006247	0.058101
VGOV	759.0	0.000083	0.005877	-0.036255	-0.003212	0.000048	0.003490	0.049138
SHEL	759.0	-0.000006	0.015414	-0.124236	-0.006485	0.000166	0.007576	0.110182
INRG	759.0	0.000893	0.018961	-0.127039	-0.007182	0.001337	0.010414	0.085252

Table 8: Logarithmic returns transposition, 2019 to 2022.

Table.9, shows the correlation for the testing period, and again the MPT and the CAPM were successful in providing diversification. As expected, PHGP and VGOV are negatively correlated with the FTSE100 (VUKE), while SHEL and INRG have a positive correlation.

	VUKE	PHGP	VGOV	SHEL	INRG
VUKE	1.000000	-0.016550	-0.159860	0.749309	0.598221
PHGP	-0.016550	1.000000	0.339747	0.027765	0.068975
VGOV	-0.159860	0.339747	1.000000	-0.132055	-0.033798
SHEL	0.749309	0.027765	-0.132055	1.000000	0.393076
INRG	0.598221	0.068975	-0.033798	0.393076	1.000000

Table 9: Correlation 2019 to 2022.

Figure.8 compares both portfolios' performance if £10,000 were invested in each, optimised in green and random in blue. They move in the same directions most of the time. However, the random portfolio is volatile, shooting up to £16,000 by the end of 2020 and losing half its gains in the beginning of 2021. The optimised portfolio accumulated more than 10% returns and stagnated around that for most of the period. The random portfolio is illiquid and risky but extremely profitable.

Figure 8: Optimised (green) and random (blue) portfolios' performance if £10,000 were invested in each.

Result

In terms of algorithmic trading, the MCS has limitations. Algorithmic trading has no attention to economic details like liquidity and risk. Effectivity is usually measured by the Sharpe ratio (Portilla, 2022).

However, in economic terms, the MCS was effective, bringing a result that was not expected from it. The MCS, expected to underperform during economic shocks, optimised the portfolio by diminishing risk during two unexpected crises, Covid-19 and now the war in Ukraine. Economic shocks are not predicted, but its risks can be minimised by the CAPM, the MPT and the MCS. This result is possible, because the portfolio to be optimised was created considering economics and finance theory, optimising the asset that brought consistent returns, paying monthly dividends with the lower volatility.

Moreover, the portfolio's average beta in the construction was risk averse (0.664). Figure.8 exemplifies that the optimised portfolio moved accordingly, while the random was quite aggressive, which could be a terrible surprise for the investor.

There are a few reasons why the MCS did not assigned PHGP a higher weight in the portfolio. First, in the period used to build the portfolio, 2014-2019, the gold market faced shocks, red in figure.9, between 2014-2015 and 2017-2018, and the end of 2019 prices were collapsing again. The gold market ended up outperforming the market in 2020 due to the Covid-19 outbreak.

Figure 9: Gold (PHGP) shocks in red. Source: Bloomberg, 2022.

Second, due to the high volatility and the lack of dividend payment, the asset is not liquid. Its minimisation in the MCS makes sense considering the CAPM, the MPT and the historical prices for the period. The period to be analysed is important. This experiment did not choose 2020 as the analysing

period, as 3 years were chosen to do the empirical test. If the sample had comprised 2020, year that gold outperformed the market, the MCS output could be different, even though the asset experienced volatility. Again, another consideration the economist must pay attention.

Therefore, the MCS is an effective tool to maximise a portfolio, by assigning weights to it. However, it is a tool, and the economist behind the MCS operation needs to address requisites when building the portfolio to be maximised. If theoretical demands are not followed, and the investor builds the portfolio without proper guidelines, the experiment may be a disaster.

Conclusion

The MCS is used when the probability distribution is hard to derive analytically, most of the times because the data is not simple and does not have a well-behaved probability distribution. Therefore, the simulation allows rare events to be modelled (Pedersen, 2014).

However, the MCS and the MPT focus on complex mathematical modelling and formulas to support assumptions. The findings are usually presented using unnecessarily complicated rhetoric and formulaic expressions (Mangram E., 2013).

Furthermore, most papers apply the MCS to predict real-world events, but few evaluate the performance with the real-world data, with the exception for Lombardi and Sgherri (2007). It is the same as predicting tomorrows, but not assessing the prediction outcome few days later. This is the gap that this paper addressed, by applying an empirical test and testing empirically a highly empirical methodology as the MCS. This test is extremely important, as the MCS is already widely used in Economics and Finance. Another gap this study addressed, was the use of theory and premisses supported by the CAPM and the MPT when building the model.

The results were surprising, as the period chosen is unusual. The UK has been facing subsequent crises, Brexit, Covid-19, and the war in Ukraine, causing historical prices to follow unpredictable paths. Using a simplistic view of an algorithmic trader, the portfolio optimised did not optimised gains at lower volatility, Sharpe ratio. However, an economist will notice that the portfolio was optimised, as in a risky time, the portfolio diminished risks and brought predictable and consistent gains.

This study could not test different portfolios with different betas, and test whether the result would be the same in different risk profiles. Future studies could expand this empirical test and discover if the findings match when you add different portfolios.

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Appendix

Tables

Weight Bounds	Portfolio Weights (Long Only)					Value Yield		Kelly Value	Pr*
	S&P 500	Coca-Cola	Wal-Mart	McDonald's	Gov. Bond	Mean	Stdev		
[0, 0.1]	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.6	6.8%	0.2%	0.0658	0.0
[0, 0.2]	0.2	0.2	0.2	0.2	0.2	10.1%	0.3%	0.0962	0.0
[0, 0.3]	0.3	0.3	0.3	0.1	0.0	12.5%	0.4%	0.1178	1.0
[0, 0.4]	0.2	0.4	0.4	0.0	0.0	13.9%	0.5%	0.1300	1.0
[0, 0.5]	0.0	0.5	0.5	0.0	0.0	15.2%	0.6%	0.1415	1.0
[0, 0.6]	0.0	0.6	0.4	0.0	0.0	15.5%	0.7%	0.1441	1.0
[0, 0.7]	0.0	0.7	0.3	0.0	0.0	15.8%	0.8%	0.1467	1.0
[0, 0.8]	0.0	0.8	0.2	0.0	0.0	16.1%	1.0%	0.1493	1.0
[0, 0.9]	0.0	0.9	0.1	0.0	0.0	16.4%	1.1%	0.1519	1.0
[0, 1.0]	0.0	1.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	16.7%	1.2%	0.1545	1.0

Table 1: Kelly optimal portfolio weights, long-only. All assets except from Coca-Cola would be removed with time, to maximise the Kelly value. Holding period is eternity. (Pedersen, 2014, pg.94).

	Portfolio Weights (Long Only)				Value Yield	
	S&P 500	Coca-Cola	Wal-Mart	McDonald's	Mean	Stdev
Inefficient Frontier	0.000	0.000	0.000	1.000	0.079	0.004
	0.523	0.000	0.013	0.463	0.084	0.004
	0.475	0.000	0.100	0.425	0.089	0.003
	0.424	0.014	0.166	0.397	0.093	0.003
	0.371	0.030	0.229	0.370	0.098	0.003
	0.319	0.046	0.292	0.344	0.102	0.003
	0.266	0.062	0.354	0.318	0.107	0.003
Min-Variance	0.240	0.070	0.385	0.305	0.110	0.003
Efficient Frontier	0.214	0.078	0.417	0.291	0.112	0.003
	0.162	0.094	0.480	0.265	0.116	0.003
	0.109	0.109	0.543	0.238	0.121	0.003
	0.057	0.125	0.605	0.212	0.126	0.003
	0.005	0.141	0.668	0.186	0.130	0.003
	0.000	0.157	0.726	0.117	0.135	0.003
	0.000	0.172	0.783	0.045	0.139	0.004
	0.000	0.239	0.761	0.000	0.144	0.004
	0.000	0.391	0.609	0.000	0.149	0.005
	0.000	0.543	0.457	0.000	0.153	0.006
	0.000	0.696	0.304	0.000	0.158	0.008
	0.000	0.848	0.152	0.000	0.163	0.010
	0.000	1.000	0.000	0.000	0.167	0.012

Table 2: Mean-variance portfolio weights, long-only. McDonalds is in most of the efficient frontier, even giving lower returns, as it has lower variance. Holding period is eternity. (Pedersen, 2014, pg.89).

	count	mean	std	min	25%	50%	75%	max
VUKE	1288.0	0.000186	0.008164	-0.044329	-0.004105	0.000432	0.004366	0.043370
PHGP	1288.0	0.000186	0.009114	-0.033097	-0.004609	-0.000257	0.004894	0.121917
VGOV	1288.0	0.000188	0.004310	-0.013345	-0.002290	0.000208	0.002857	0.023380
SHEL	1288.0	0.000270	0.012962	-0.063886	-0.006387	0.000175	0.007070	0.054084
INRG	1288.0	0.000200	0.012226	-0.054934	-0.006196	0.000394	0.007368	0.054809

Table 3: Logarithmic returns transposition, 2014 to 2019.

	VUKE	PHGP	VGOV	SHEL	INRG
VUKE	0.016797	-0.002205	-0.001881	0.017533	0.015766
PHGP	-0.002205	0.020934	0.003828	0.001652	0.001487
VGOV	-0.001881	0.003828	0.004681	-0.002209	-0.001583
SHEL	0.017533	0.001652	-0.002209	0.042340	0.019020
INRG	0.015766	0.001487	-0.001583	0.019020	0.037668

Table 4: Covariance 2014 to 2019.

	VUKE	PHGP	VGOV	SHEL	INRG
VUKE	1.000000	-0.117583	-0.212156	0.657446	0.626767
PHGP	-0.117583	1.000000	0.386671	0.055490	0.052970
VGOV	-0.212156	0.386671	1.000000	-0.156910	-0.119228
SHEL	0.657446	0.055490	-0.156910	1.000000	0.476274
INRG	0.626767	0.052970	-0.119228	0.476274	1.000000

Table 5: Correlation 2014 to 2019.

RANDOM Portfolio						
	VUKE	PHGP	VGOV	SHEL	INRG	Portfolio (Total)
weights	0.24	0.1998	0.1168	0.182	0.2614	1.000
daily ret	0.00003504	0.00009710	0.00000969	-0.00000109	0.00023343	0.00037418
daily std	0.00228912	0.00195924	0.00068643	0.00280535	0.00495641	0.012696546
					Sharpe ratio	0.029470645
Beta	0.24024	-0.0085914	-0.0057232	0.252434	0.2676736	0.746033

Table 6: Random portfolio results, 2019-2022.

OPTIMISED Portfolio						
	VUKE	PHGP	VGOV	SHEL	INRG	Portfolio (Total)
weights	0.158	0.0448	0.71	0.0666	0.0206	1.000
daily ret	0.0000231	0.0000218	0.0000589	-0.0000004	0.0000184	0.0001218
daily std	0.0015070	0.0004393	0.0041727	0.0010266	0.0003906	0.007536152
					Sharpe ratio	0.016157716
Beta	0.158158	-0.001926	-0.03479	0.0923742	0.0210944	0.2349102

Table 7: Optimised portfolio results, 2019-2022.

	count	mean	std	min	25%	50%	75%	max
VUKE	759.0	0.000146	0.009538	-0.081088	-0.003665	0.000511	0.004763	0.062951
PHGP	759.0	0.000486	0.009813	-0.049732	-0.004422	0.000539	0.006247	0.058101
VGOV	759.0	0.000083	0.005877	-0.036255	-0.003212	0.000048	0.003490	0.049138
SHEL	759.0	-0.000006	0.015414	-0.124236	-0.006485	0.000166	0.007576	0.110182
INRG	759.0	0.000893	0.018961	-0.127039	-0.007182	0.001337	0.010414	0.085252

Table 8: Logarithmic returns transposition, 2019 to 2022.

	VUKE	PHGP	VGOV	SHEL	INRG
VUKE	1.000000	-0.016550	-0.159860	0.749309	0.598221
PHGP	-0.016550	1.000000	0.339747	0.027765	0.068975
VGOV	-0.159860	0.339747	1.000000	-0.132055	-0.033798
SHEL	0.749309	0.027765	-0.132055	1.000000	0.393076
INRG	0.598221	0.068975	-0.033798	0.393076	1.000000

Table 9: Correlation 2019 to 2022.

Images

Figure 1: Diminishing specific risk with diversification. Based on Pike, Neale and Linsley (2012, pg.209)

Figure 2: Portfolio's normalised returns 2014 to 2019.

Figure 3: Portfolio's log daily return 2014 to 2019.

Figure 4: Kernel Density Estimate 2014 to 2019.

Figure 5: MCS efficient frontier plot, red dot is the optimised portfolio 2014 to 2019.

Figure 6: Portfolio's empirical test logarithmic daily return 2019 to 2022.

Figure 7: Empirical test's Kernel density estimate 2019 to 2022.

Figure 8: Optimised (green) and random (blue) portfolios' performance if £10,000 were invested in each.

Figure 9: Gold (PHGP) shocks in red. Source: Bloomberg, 2022.